

AsyMov: Integrated Sensing and Communications with Asynchronous Moving Devices

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Abstract—Estimating the Doppler frequency shift caused by moving targets is one of the key objectives of Integrated Sensing And Communication (ISAC) systems, as it enables applications such as target classification, human activity recognition, and gait analysis. In practical scenarios, Doppler estimation is hindered by the movement of transmitter and receiver devices, and by the phase offsets caused by their clock asynchrony. Existing approaches have *separately* addressed these two aspects, either assuming clock-synchronous moving devices or asynchronous static ones. In fact, jointly tackling device motion and clock asynchrony is extremely challenging, as the Doppler shift from device movement differs for each propagation path and the phase offsets are time-varying. In this work, we present AsyMov, a method to estimate the bistatic Doppler frequency of a target and its velocity in ISAC setups featuring *mobile and asynchronous* devices. It leverages the channel impulse response at the receiver, by originally exploiting the invariance of phase offsets across propagation paths and the bistatic geometry, where the target Doppler and the device velocity are jointly estimated by a newly proposed alternating minimization algorithm. Moreover, it can be seamlessly integrated with device velocity measurements obtained from onboard sensors (if available), for enhanced reliability. Here, AsyMov is thoroughly characterized by way of theory (Cramér-Rao bound), simulation, and experiments, implementing it on an IEEE 802.11ay testbed and testing it on multiple setups in the 60 GHz and 28 GHz bands, including moving human subjects. Numerical and experimental results show superior performance against state-of-the-art methods and are on par with scenarios featuring *static* ISAC devices.

Index Terms—Integrated sensing and communication, Doppler estimation, velocity estimation, target mobility, synchronization, Wi-Fi sensing, mobile devices, Doppler frequency.

I. INTRODUCTION

Integrated Sensing And Communication (ISAC) is expected to be a cornerstone of future wireless communication systems [1]. One of the key uses of ISAC concerns the estimation of the Doppler frequency caused by a moving target, which also reveals its velocity. On the one hand, Doppler estimation enhances the sensing resolution of the system, as it allows distinguishing targets moving at different speeds [2]. On the other hand, the Doppler effect can be leveraged by a wide range of fine-grained cellular and Wi-Fi sensing applications, such as person identification based on gait [3], fall detection [4], drone

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Fig. 1: Overview of AsyMov.

monitoring [5], and human movement classification for smart homes and remote healthcare [6], [7].

Compared to indoor radar systems, Doppler estimation in ISAC poses several challenges. First, ISAC transmitter (TX) and receiver (RX) devices are spatially separated (bistatic), so they rely on *asynchronous* Local Oscillators (LOs) to generate the carrier signal, which is consequently affected by a time-varying relative drift [8]. This causes Timing Offset (TO), Carrier Frequency Offset (CFO), and a random Phase Offset (PO) across different transmissions. CFO and PO prevent the coherent processing of channel measurements across time, which is required for Doppler estimation [9].

The reference scenario that we consider in the present work is depicted in Fig. 1. It features a TX/RX pair where one of these two devices is mobile, and the target is also moving. For this setup, differently from what is commonly assumed in ISAC research, an *additional* Doppler frequency contribution appears on the reflected signal due to the movement of the TX or RX device. The key challenge in *jointly* addressing clock asynchrony and moving TX/RX devices descends from the different properties of CFO/PO and from the motion-induced Doppler component of the TX/RX device, which adds up to the Doppler caused by the target. In fact, the noise due to CFO/PO is the same for all propagation paths [10] (spatial domain), but changes across subsequent communication packets (time domain), whereas the device Doppler changes slowly over time but causes a different frequency shift on each propagation path. We underline that existing techniques based on cross-antenna processing, [8], or reference paths, [10], [11], cannot concurrently cope with these different spatial and temporal dynamics. In fact, existing solutions only address the following scenarios: (i) *moving* monostatic radar systems, which are not affected by CFO and PO [12]–[14] and only need to compensate for the device Doppler shift, or (ii) asynchronous ISAC systems with *static* devices [9], [10], [15], which are only affected by CFO and PO. Either case poses stringent assumptions to the application scenario, limiting the range of use of previous solutions.

In this work, we propose AsyMov, a method to estimate

the Doppler frequency of a target and the device velocity in bistatic mobile ISAC setups using the sole wireless signal. To this end, we leverage the growing trend in next-generation wireless systems of adopting a large communication bandwidth [16]. This yields a good multipath resolution, which can be exploited to extract *path-specific signal features*.

Our approach (see Fig. 1) obtains phase measurements at the RX from different multipath reflections across time in the Channel Impulse Response (CIR). Hence, it removes CFO and PO by leveraging their invariance across the received propagation paths. Path-specific phase terms are subsequently removed via time-domain phase differencing, thanks to their slow varying nature over short time windows. Most importantly, each multipath component is *differently* affected by the TX or RX motion, and we exploit this as a source of *diversity* to reduce the number of unknowns in the phase measurements model. As a result, we can successfully cast the Doppler frequency estimation of the target as a non-linear system of equations, that can be solved if at least two multipath components from static scatterers are available. In such a case, the target's Doppler and the ISAC device velocity are jointly estimated via a newly proposed and efficient alternating minimization algorithm that operates on time-averaged phase measurements. Remarkably, AsyMov is robust to *irregular* sampling of the CIR. This means that it can be implemented in ISAC systems with minimal overhead, by opportunistically exploiting the transmissions of data packets, and without requiring the transmission of additional signals for sensing purposes or applying sparse channel reconstruction methods [17]. As an additional feature, AsyMov can seamlessly integrate measurements of any moving device velocity obtained with an onboard Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU), which may be available on mobile devices. As we show in Section VI, our experimental results reveal that the integration of an onboard IMU leads to less accurate results than using our approach with the sole wireless signal, but increases the estimation reliability in case fewer than two static multipath components are available.

AsyMov is extensively evaluated along two lines. First, its performance limits are analyzed by obtaining the Cramér-Rao Bound (CRB) for the target's Doppler frequency estimation and via numerical simulations. Second, it is evaluated on real measurements obtained with an IEEE 802.11ay ISAC system operating in the 60 or 28 GHz bands. AsyMov is finally compared against standard Doppler estimation techniques based on Multiple Signal Classification (MUSIC) [18] and to the case where both TX and RX are static.

The contributions of this paper are summarized as follows.

- 1) We solve the problem of estimating the Doppler frequency of a target and the TX/RX device velocity in bistatic ISAC with asynchronous *moving* devices. Our solution uniquely relies on the analysis of the received wireless signal by means of an original CIR phase measurements differencing step and a new alternating minimization algorithm.
- 2) We derive the CRB for Doppler frequency estimation based on our measurement model and propose a more practical, approximate CRB expression. Using numerical simulations, we show that AsyMov achieves accurate

Doppler frequency estimation with different carrier frequencies and Signal-to-Noise Ratios (SNRs).

- 3) We evaluate AsyMov performance on real measurements, collected with an IEEE 802.11ay testbed at 60 and 28 GHz, in different setups. Our results show that AsyMov achieves median estimation errors as low as 3 Hz for the Doppler frequency, 3° for device movement direction, and 2 cm/s for the device speed.
- 4) We demonstrate improvements over existing MUSIC-based methods [18], combined with JUMP [10] for asynchrony compensation. Moreover, AsyMov is more accurate than a benchmark algorithm that estimates the device movement with an onboard IMU sensor, and it can be easily integrated with IMU measurements when the number of multipath components in the CIR is insufficient.

The paper is organized as follows. The related work is discussed in Section II. Reference scenario and system model are introduced in Section III. AsyMov is presented in Section IV. Section V contains its analysis, with the derivation of the CRB and related numerical results. Experimental results are shown in Section VI, to demonstrate the effectiveness of our approach against state-of-the-art methods. Concluding remarks are given in Section VII.

II. RELATED WORK

Synchronous ISAC. Monostatic full-duplex technology for ISAC has been investigated in many research works. In [19], [20], beamforming, waveform optimization, and phased array architectures have been utilized to enable full-duplex ISAC in Millimeter-Wave (mmWave) 5G systems. The authors of [17], [21] focused on micro-Doppler spectrogram estimation for indoor human sensing, using a monostatic full-duplex IEEE 802.11ay system. However, full-duplex technology suffers from strong self-interference which remains a challenging and still open issue [19]. As a solution, the transmitted power can be reduced to avoid saturation at the receiver, but this is only feasible in small indoor scenarios and reduces the communication SNR [21]. Other works [22]–[24] have addressed bistatic Doppler estimation through linear methods in mmWave ISAC, assuming synchronized static devices.

Since synchronous transceivers are unaffected by CFO and PO, the above works apply standard techniques from time-frequency analysis to obtain the target's Doppler shift. However, with asynchronous time systems and moving devices, these methods fail due to the superposition of the phase offsets, the device movement, and the target's Doppler frequency.

Bistatic asynchronous ISAC. Existing works on bistatic ISAC which tackled the clock asynchronism between TX and RX can be categorized into two groups.

The first group exploits the fact that the clock offsets across multiple antennas at the RX are the same due to the shared LO. In [25], the authors propose the Cross-Antenna Cross-Correlation (CACC) method to remove TO and CFO. Similarly, [26]–[28] use the Cross-Antenna Signal Ratio (CASR) method, which removes phase offsets by obtaining the ratio of the channel state information between antennas and enables

Doppler estimation. Authors in [27] analyze CASR using the Mobius transform to estimate the Doppler frequency shift with the Long-Range wide area (LoRa) technology. In [28], instead, multi-person respiration sensing is modeled as a blind source separation problem and efficiently solved by independent component analysis. Cross-antenna methods require multiple antennas at the receiver, which becomes costly at higher frequencies (such as in mmWave systems), where typically phased arrays are preferred. Moreover, they add complexity to the estimation of the sensing parameters by introducing non-linearity.

The second group of works exploits a reference propagation path. [29] proposes a new low-complexity method relying on the correlation between Line-of-Sight (LoS) and Non-Line-of-Sight (NLoS) paths to compensate for the CFO. After the compensation, the Doppler frequency is estimated through Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT). [10] proposes a correlation-based algorithm to compensate for the CFO which is robust to multitarget and NLoS scenarios to compute the micro-Doppler spectrum via a short-time DFT.

The above bistatic ISAC methods all assume *static* TX and RX, which poses severe limitations to real-world ISAC applications. The device movement introduces an additional Doppler frequency shift, which *differs* for each propagation path and can not be tackled by the mentioned methods.

More recently, [30], [31] have proposed a fingerprint-based TO and CFO removal method for vehicular scenarios. However, the Doppler introduced by a moving TX or RX is not considered as a disturbance factor for the target Doppler estimation, so these works inherit the above limitations.

Mobile transceiver ISAC. Existing solutions for wireless sensing with moving devices mostly consider dedicated monostatic mmWave radars. This avoids self-interference, CFO, and PO, and makes the problem significantly simpler. In [12] and [13], the Doppler phase information is extracted by removing the effect of device motion using reflections on background static objects. Recently, the authors of [14] introduced the dynamic Fresnel zone model to link the variation in the received signal and the receiver movement. However, this work does not provide a method to estimate the Doppler frequency of the target and focuses instead on activity recognition.

To the best of our knowledge, ISAC with asynchronous and mobile devices has only been considered in our previous work [32], since other works all consider *static* ISAC devices. This work presents important novel contributions compared to [32], as detailed in the following.

- [32] relies on standard Nonlinear Least-Squares (NLS), whereas we propose an original, more efficient solution based on alternating minimization and analyze its identifiability and convergence.
- We provide a theoretical analysis of the sensitivity of the Doppler estimation to noise and multipath channel parameters, which is missing in [32].
- We perform an extensive experimental campaign in several scenarios using an IEEE 802.11ay Radio Frequency System on a Chip (RFSoc) ISAC system, validating our algorithm on real data at 60 and 28 GHz, whereas [32] relies on simulations.

- [32] assumes a constant channel estimation period, which is unrealistic in ISAC. Conversely, AsyMov is robust to irregular channel estimation (sampling) times.

III. MOBILE ISAC SYSTEM MODEL

In this section, we introduce the mobile ISAC system model. This includes the reference scenario, the channel model, and the expressions of the phase measurements.

A. Reference scenario

Consider two ISAC devices acting, respectively, as transmitter (TX) and receiver (RX), located on a 2-dimensional (2D), horizontal Cartesian plane. Denote by t the continuous time variable, and refer to $\mathbf{x}^{\text{tx}}(t)$ and $\mathbf{x}^{\text{rx}}(t)$ as the time-varying locations of the TX and RX devices, respectively. In the following, we consider the TX to be mobile, while the RX is static, i.e., $\mathbf{x}^{\text{rx}}(t) = \mathbf{x}^{\text{rx}}$. We call $v^{\text{tx}}(t)$ and $\eta(t)$ the TX speed and movement direction with respect to the LoS segment between TX and RX. Note that this assumption is not restrictive, since the symmetric case in which the RX moves and the TX is static is analogous, as further discussed in Section III-B, and leads to similar derivations. Note also that our model still holds if the TX and RX are both mobile. In this case, we consider $v^{\text{tx}}(t), \eta(t)$ to be the *relative* velocity magnitude and the direction between the TX and the RX.

We consider Q static or mobile scatterers in the environment, indexed by $q = 1, \dots, Q$, each at location $\mathbf{x}_q(t)$. Mobile scatterers have a velocity $v_q(t)$ that forms an angle $\gamma_q(t)$ with the bisector line of the angle formed by the TX, the scatterer, and the RX, denoted by $\beta_q(t)$ (*bistatic angle*), as shown in Fig. 2. We aim to estimate the bistatic Doppler frequency caused by a moving scatterer of interest, called *target* using channel estimates obtained by the RX as part of normal communication and Angle of Departure (AoD) estimates. In the symmetric case where the RX moves, the AoD would be replaced by the Angle of Arrival (AoA) (see Section III-B).

B. Channel model

Consider the wireless signal transmitted by the TX device. We call $\lambda = c/f_c$ the wavelength of the transmitted signal carrier, with c being the speed of light and f_c the carrier frequency. We consider a multipath channel including Q delayed, Doppler-shifted, and attenuated copies of the transmitted signal, caused by the Q scatterers in the environment. As customary in the ISAC literature, we only consider first-order signal reflections and the LoS propagation path, since these are significantly stronger than second-order reflections [33].

Next, we present the Doppler frequency model and the continuous-time channel model underlying the considered scenario. Then, we derive the practical discrete-time channel estimated by the ISAC system.

1) *Doppler frequency model:* The TX movement causes an instantaneous Doppler shift on the LoS path, obtained as the derivative of the LoS path length with respect to time [34]

$$f_{\text{D,LoS}}^{\text{tx}}(t) = \frac{1}{\lambda} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \|\mathbf{x}^{\text{rx}} - \mathbf{x}^{\text{tx}}(t)\| \approx \frac{v^{\text{tx}}(t)}{\lambda} \cos \eta(t), \quad (1)$$

Fig. 2: Reference scenario and multipath geometry. The time dependency is omitted for better visualization.

The approximation in Eq. (1) holds for short processing intervals, during which we consider the movement of the TX to be well approximated by a constant-velocity model [34]. We remark that the Doppler due to the movement of the TX or RX is not modeled in recent works that tackle asynchronous bistatic ISAC systems, e.g., [10], [30].

The Doppler frequency on a bistatic path q is obtained by differentiating its path length with respect to time as [34]

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\lambda} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\|\mathbf{x}^{\text{rx}} - \mathbf{x}_q(t)\| + \|\mathbf{x}_q(t) - \mathbf{x}^{\text{tx}}(t)\|) &\approx (2) \\ &\approx \underbrace{\frac{v^{\text{tx}}(t)}{\lambda} \cos \xi_q(t)}_{f_{\text{D},q}^{\text{tx}}(t)} + \underbrace{\frac{2v_q(t)}{\lambda} \cos \gamma_q(t) \cos \frac{\beta_q(t)}{2}}_{f_{\text{D},q}(t)}, \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

where $\xi_q(t)$ is the angle between the segment connecting the q -th scatterer to the TX and the TX velocity vector.

Eq. (3) shows that the movement of the target causes an additional Doppler shift on the reflected signal. Moreover, the target-induced bistatic Doppler frequency shift depends on the direction of motion with respect to the bistatic system. In this paper, we do not estimate the moving velocity vector of the target, given by the pair $v_q(t), \gamma_q(t)$ (or in Cartesian coordinates), but only the aggregate Doppler shift $f_{\text{D},q}(t)$. Hence, we do not require the knowledge of $\gamma_q(t), \beta_q(t)$, nor estimate them. The estimation of the velocity vector is, in general, ambiguous using a single bistatic TX and RX pair [34], and is solved for multistatic scenarios [35]. We focus instead on the estimation of the Doppler frequency in the unsolved case of moving TX-RX *and* presence of CFO, so the ambiguity does not arise in our model that considers $f_{\text{D},q}(t)$ as a whole. In multistatic settings, the Doppler frequency estimated by AsyMov on each bistatic pair can be used as the input for velocity vector estimation algorithms.

2) *Continuous-time channel model:* Consider the continuous-time channel between the TX and the RX and denote by $\tau_q(t)$, $\alpha_q(t)$, and $A_q(t)$ the propagation delay, the AoD, and the complex coefficient of the q -th path, respectively. $A_q(t)$ accounts for the propagation loss, and the scatterer's Radar Cross-Section (RCS) [2]. If the devices are equipped with multiple antennas, $A_q(t)$ also includes the combined effect of the TX and RX beamforming vectors.

As shown in Fig. 2, we consider the AoD to be measured relatively to the LoS line connecting the TX and the RX. This assumes that the orientation of the RX with respect to the TX is known and has been compensated for. This could be done by obtaining the AoD or AoA estimate of the LoS path, for example, during beam-alignment protocols for

communication. We use this technique in our experimental evaluation in Section VI. If available, an alternative is to use onboard sensors like an IMU to estimate the device orientation.

The offsets caused by the asynchrony of TX and RX, i.e., TO, CFO, and PO are denoted by $\tau_o(t)$, $f_o(t)$, and $\psi_o(t)$, respectively. Denoting by $\delta(\tau)$ the Dirac delta function, the CIR at time t and delay τ is

$$h(t, \tau) = e^{j\psi_o(t)} \sum_{q=1}^Q A_q(t) e^{j\vartheta_q(t)} \delta(\tau - \tau_q(t) - \tau_o(t)), \quad (4)$$

where $\vartheta_q(t) = 2\pi(f_{\text{D},q}(t) + f_o(t) + f_{\text{D},q}^{\text{tx}}(t))t$. Note that $f_{\text{D},q}(t)$ is added to the CFO and the Doppler shift introduced by the transmitter.

We stress that even though AsyMov requires estimating the AoD (if the TX moves) or AoA (if the RX moves) of the reflections, it does not require having multiple antennas on the ISAC devices. Indeed, our approach is agnostic to the number of available antennas or radio frequency chains at the TX or RX, and can be implemented on cost-effective phased-array systems. In this case, the AoD or AoA can be obtained through correlation-based algorithms such as the ones in [21], [36].

3) *CIR estimate model:* In Single Carrier (SC) systems, e.g., IEEE 802.11ay, the RX estimates the CIR directly using cross-correlation of the received signal with a known pilot sequence such as complementary Golay sequences which exhibit perfect autocorrelation property with no frequency shift. In Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) systems, e.g., 5G-NR, an estimate of the Channel Frequency Response (CFR) is computed at the receiver by exploiting a known preamble. The CIR can then be obtained via Inverse Discrete Fourier Transform (IDFT) of the estimated CFR. We denote by G the SNR gain given by coherent processing of several pilot symbols during channel estimation. This is equal to the length of the pilot sequence if standard matched filtering or frequency-domain symbol division are used, otherwise it can be estimated empirically. G will be used in the model of the noise distribution on the resulting CIR in Section III-C. In this paper, we do not use the random data part of the communication packets to estimate the channel. Nevertheless, AsyMov could be applied to the data symbols without modification, after demodulating and decoding them.

As a consequence of the finite bandwidth of the ISAC system, two or more scatterers may be closer than the delay resolution, given by $\Delta_\tau = 1/B$ where B is the TX signal bandwidth. Hence, we consider a multipath channel including $M(t) \leq Q$ resolvable components, indexed by $m = 1, \dots, M(t)$. The estimated CIR is discretized in the delay domain with granularity Δ_τ and the discrete delay grid is given by $l\Delta_\tau, l = 0, \dots, L-1$, where L is the grid span.

The CIR estimation is repeated across multiple time frames, indexed by k , at instants $t_k, k = 0, \dots, K-1$, where K is the number of frames and we consider $t_0 = 0$ s. We denote the inter-frame spacing by $T_k = t_k - t_{k-1}$. Note that the inter-frame spacing can be irregular, i.e., channel estimation does not need to happen on a regular sampling grid.

Using a common assumption in ISAC and radar processing, we consider a short processing window of duration

t_{K-1} [33], where the parameters, $M(t)$, $\tau_m(t)$, $f_{D,m}(t)$, $\alpha_m(t)$, $A_m(t)$, $\eta(t)$, $\xi_m(t)$, $v^{\text{tx}}(t)$, and consequently the TX motion-induced Doppler shift $f_{D,m}^{\text{tx}}(t)$ can be considered constant. Conversely, all the nuisance parameters, $\tau_o(t)$, $f_o(t)$, $\psi_o(t)$, are time-varying within the window. Note that, although the CFO is sometimes considered slowly time-varying, in ISAC it can significantly drift during the processing window of K frames. Moreover, in some systems, we need to consider the *residual* CFO after partial compensation by the receiver. The residual CFO is fast time-varying, being the random residual of an imperfect estimation and compensation process [9].

The noise-free estimated CIR at the k -th frame is

$$h[k, l] = e^{j\psi_o(t_k)} \sum_{m=1}^M A_m e^{j\vartheta_m[k]} \chi(l\Delta\tau - \tau_m - \tau_o(t_k)), \quad (5)$$

where $\vartheta_m[k] = 2\pi(f_{D,m} + f_o(t_k) + f_{D,m}^{\text{tx}})t_k$. In Eq. (5), $\chi(l\Delta\tau)$ replaces the Dirac delta to account for non-ideal autocorrelation of the pilot sequence (in SC systems) or the impact of the finite-length CFR estimate (in OFDM systems).

In our scenario, we consider that the M propagation paths can be partitioned as follows: (i) a LoS path, which represents the direct propagation from the TX to the RX, (ii) a single moving target path, (iii) S *static* scatterers paths for which $f_{D,m} = 0$. Point (ii) is not a requirement for AsyMov, but simplifies the derivation. If multiple targets are present, AsyMov should be applied on each corresponding peak in the CIR. Note that assumption (i) simplifies the description of the algorithm, but is not strictly required. In fact, AsyMov is still applicable when the LoS is not available, by replacing the LoS path with a reference static path caused by a strong scatterer.

In practice, TX could also measure v^{tx} using an onboard IMU, simplifying the derivation of the target's Doppler frequency. However, the accuracy of such measurement is critical to the subsequent estimation process as discussed in [10]. Since low-cost sensors available on commercial cellular devices are often inaccurate, our approach considers v^{tx} to be unknown, i.e., it relies on the sole wireless signal. Still, our algorithm can readily incorporate a reliable estimate of v^{tx} from an IMU. This is demonstrated in Section VI-D, where we show that AsyMov is more accurate when only using the wireless signal, but external IMU measurements enhance its reliability when multipath components are momentarily undetected. Next, we focus on estimating the target Doppler frequency under the nuisance due to the CFO, PO, and the TX motion. Hence, we assume that the RX can detect and separate the M multipath components and extract their phase across time. To this end, the TO can be compensated for by obtaining *relative* delay measurements with respect to the LoS, as done in [10].

C. Phase measurements

In this section, we provide a model of the phase for each multipath component in Eq. (5).

We group the CFO and PO terms, which are the same on all propagation paths, into $\Psi_o(t_k) = \psi_o(t_k) + 2\pi f_o(t_k)t_k$. Moreover, we use subscripts \cdot_{LoS} and \cdot_t to refer to quantities related to the LoS and to the target-induced paths, respectively,

as shown in Fig. 2. For the paths caused by static scatterers, we use index $s = 1, \dots, S$, where S is the number of resolvable static scatterers detected in the processing window, with $S = M - 2$. The phase of the LoS is

$$\phi_{\text{LoS}}[k] = \Psi_o(t_k) + \angle A_{\text{LoS}} + 2\pi t_k \left(\frac{v^{\text{tx}}}{\lambda} \cos \eta \right) + w_{\text{LoS}}[k], \quad (6)$$

where $\angle \cdot$ is the phase operator, $\xi_{\text{LoS}} = \eta$, and $w_{\text{LoS}}[k]$ is the noise variable on the phase of the LoS at time k . The phase of the target-induced path is affected by both the Doppler shift caused by the target, $f_{D,t}$, and by the TX motion, v^{tx} , as

$$\phi_t[k] = \Psi_o(t_k) + \angle A_t + 2\pi t_k \left(f_{D,t} + \frac{v^{\text{tx}}}{\lambda} \cos \xi_t \right) + w_t[k], \quad (7)$$

where ξ_t is the angle between the segment connecting the target to the TX and the TX velocity vector, and $w_t[k]$ is the noise variable on the phase of the target path at time k . The phase of the s -th static multipath component is

$$\phi_s[k] = \Psi_o(t_k) + \angle A_s + 2\pi t_k \left(\frac{v^{\text{tx}}}{\lambda} \cos \xi_s \right) + w_s[k], \quad (8)$$

where $w_s[k]$ is the noise variable on the phase of the s -th static path at time k . From the CIR, the RX measures $\text{mod}_{2\pi}(\phi_i[k])$ where $i \in \{\text{t}, \text{LoS}, s\}$, $k = 0, \dots, K - 1$, and $\text{mod}_{2\pi}(\cdot)$ is the modulo 2π division, whose result is in $[0, 2\pi)$.

D. Noise distribution on phase measurements

Before discussing the limitations of existing synchronization techniques, we analyze the distributions of the noise variables $w_{\text{LoS}}[k]$, $w_t[k]$, and $w_s[k]$. We assume the noise on the received signal is distributed as a complex Gaussian with variance σ_w^2 . We only focus on Gaussian noise because, as explained in Section IV-A, AsyMov exactly compensates for hardware impairments induced phase shifts. Therefore, the Gaussian noise on the received signal is the main nuisance source for the phase measurements. Assuming unit TX power, the corresponding *communication* SNR, based on the LoS propagation path between the TX and RX is $\text{SNR} = |A_{\text{LoS}}|^2 / \sigma_w^2$. This is the SNR we use in our simulations in Section V. Note that the communication SNR is much higher than the SNR on the target paths used for sensing, due to the much lower propagation loss affecting the LoS.

The channel estimation process reduces the noise variance by aggregating multiple pilot symbols coherently. The noise variance on the CIR is $\sigma_h^2 = \sigma_w^2 / G$ where G is the SNR gain due to channel estimation. The noise on the phase measurements in Eqs. (6-8) depends on the noise on the CIR through a non-linear relation. Denote path i in the estimated CIR in Eq. (5) at frame k by $h_i[k, l_i] \approx A_i e^{j(\vartheta_i[k] + \psi_o(t_k))}$, with $i \in \{\text{LoS}, \text{t}, s\}$. l_i is the index of the peak corresponding to the i -th path and $l_i \Delta\tau \approx \tau_i$. The real and imaginary components of $h_i[k, l_i]$ are denoted by $\Re\{h_i\}$ and $\Im\{h_i\}$, respectively. The phase of the i -th CIR path is given by $\angle h_i[k, l_i] = \arctan(\Im\{h_i\} / \Re\{h_i\})$. If the SNR on the CIR, defined as $\text{SNR}_h = G \cdot \text{SNR}$, is *high*, we can linearize the arctan function and approximate the resulting noise random variable as Gaussian. This assumption is reasonable if a sufficiently

long pilot sequence is used to estimate the channel. In this case, the noise variance on the phase of path $i \in \{\text{LoS}, t, s\}$ is given by $\sigma_{\phi_i}^2 = \sigma_h^2 / (2|A_i|^2)$ (the derivation is given in Appendix C). Therefore, the noise variables $w_{\text{LoS}}[k]$, $w_t[k]$, and $w_s[k]$, are distributed as $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\phi_i}^2)$ with $i \in \{\text{LoS}, t, s\}$.

For low SNR_h , two factors have to be accounted for: (i) the non-linearity of the arctan in the phase expression, (ii) the wrapping of the phase around 2π . An approximation of the corresponding noise probability density function resembles a von Mises distribution and is given in [37], but is outside of the scope of this paper. In Section V-C, we show that the noise distribution in the high SNR_h assumption well represents realistic scenarios in our simulations and experiments.

E. Limitations of existing techniques

Existing techniques for TO and CFO compensation use a reference antenna or propagation path to cancel out the offsets in the CIR. Using a reference propagation path as done by JUMP [10], the phase offsets removal step is

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\phi}_t[k] &= \angle \left(e^{j\phi_t[k]} / e^{j\phi_{\text{LoS}}[k]} \right) \\ &= \angle A_t - \angle A_{\text{LoS}} + 2\pi t_k \left(f_{D,t} + \frac{v^{\text{tx}}}{\lambda} (\cos \xi_t - \cos \eta) \right), \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where we omitted noise in the second expression for compactness. In Eq. (9), if the phase measurements are obtained with a regular interval $t_k = T$, one can estimate the target Doppler from a sequence of measurements using, e.g., DFT or MUSIC. This yields the desired target Doppler frequency only if the TX is *static*, i.e., $v^{\text{tx}} = 0$. If the TX moves, i.e., $v_{\text{tx}} \neq 0$, the target Doppler estimate will contain a bias equal to $v^{\text{tx}}(\cos \xi_t - \cos \eta) / \lambda$ (proportional to the TX speed), preventing the correct estimation of the target Doppler. This is exemplified in Fig. 3, where we compare the Doppler frequency estimated by AsyMov and the combination of JUMP [10] and MUSIC [18] on our experimental setup described in Section VI-B. In this case, the target and the TX are both moving with distinct velocities. JUMP correctly compensates for the CFO but can not eliminate the TX Doppler. Moreover, note that the latter is *path-specific* due to its dependency on the angle ξ_t . Hence, it is non-trivial to compensate for it using standard phase difference-based methods, since every path is differently affected by the TX movement.

Fig. 3 also shows the Doppler frequency estimated by Mobi2Sense [12] (yellow line). This compensates for the TX device motion, but can not cancel out phase offsets since it is designed for monostatic radar. As a result, the CFO and PO dominate the phase of the CIR paths, and the Doppler estimate is completely corrupted.

IV. METHODOLOGY

In this section, we introduce AsyMov, which estimates the bistatic Doppler frequency of the target from the phase measurements in Eqs. (6-8). The phase measurements are extracted from the CIR estimate as described in the previous section and shown in the left part of Fig. 4. The processing steps carried out by AsyMov are shown in the yellow block in Fig. 4 and can be summarized as follows.

Fig. 3: Example estimated target Doppler frequency with AsyMov, the combination of JUMP [10] (for TO and CFO removal) and MUSIC [18] (for Doppler estimation), and Mobi2Sense [12] in our experimental evaluation.

A. CFO and PO cancellation. The phase offsets component, Ψ_o , is common to all propagation paths. Hence, we can subtract the phase of the LoS path from the other phase measurements, by *canceling out* Ψ_o . This step does not require a direct estimation of the phase offsets, enabling coherent processing of the multipath components with minimal complexity. This is further detailed in Section IV-A.

B. Time-domain phase differencing. By computing time-domain phase differences *for each path*, we cancel out the path-specific phase terms due to the complex path amplitudes, $\angle A_i$, with $i \in \{t, \text{LoS}, s\}$, as detailed in Section IV-B. The resulting phase differences only depend on the Doppler shifts due to the TX and the target.

C. AoD-based simplification. We leverage AoD estimation at the TX and the multipath geometry to make a key simplification in the phase measurements model, as described in Section IV-C. This reduces the number of unknowns, thus enabling the estimation of the target Doppler frequency if at least 2 static multipath components are detected.

D. Doppler frequency estimation. Using the simplified phase measurements model, we formulate the estimation of the target's Doppler frequency as a non-convex optimization problem across the multipath components (see Section IV-E), that we solve using alternating minimization. To initialize the proposed algorithm, we derive and use the closed-form solution of the model using $S = 2$ static paths.

The computational steps performed by AsyMov are summarized in Algorithm 1, to which we refer in the detailed description provided in the next sections. Finally, we highlight the fact that a multi-target scenario would not increase the number of required static paths, as it would be sufficient to repeat Algorithm 1 initializing it each time with one different target phase ϕ_t for every available target in the environment.

A. CFO and PO cancellation

To cancel out the phase offsets term, Ψ_o , we use Eq. (9) as shown in line 2 of Algorithm 1, obtaining

$$\tilde{\phi}_t[k] = \Omega_t + 2\pi t_k \left(f_{D,t} + \frac{v^{\text{tx}}}{\lambda} (\cos \xi_t - \cos \eta) \right) + w'_t[k], \quad (10)$$

$$\tilde{\phi}_s[k] = \Omega_s + 2\pi t_k \left(\frac{v^{\text{tx}}}{\lambda} (\cos \xi_s - \cos \eta) \right) + w'_s[k], \quad (11)$$

Fig. 4: Block diagram of the proposed phase measurements steps and algorithm.

Algorithm 1 AsyMov algorithm.

Input: Phase measurements $\phi_{\text{LoS}}[k]$, $\phi_t[k]$, $\phi_s[k]$, $s = 1, \dots, S$.

Output: Estimates of the parameters $\hat{f}_{\text{D,t}}$, \hat{v}^{tx} , $\hat{\eta}$.

- 1: **for** $k = 0, \dots, K - 1$ **do**
- 2: $\tilde{\phi}_i[k] = \angle \left(\frac{e^{j\tilde{\phi}_i[k]}}{e^{j\phi_{\text{LoS}}[k]}} \right)$ (CFO and PO cancellation)
- 3: $\Delta_i[k] = \angle \left(\frac{e^{j\tilde{\phi}_i[k]}}{e^{j\tilde{\phi}_i[k-1]}} \right)$ (time domain differencing)
- 4: $\tilde{\Delta}_i[k] = \Delta_i[k] / (2\pi T_k)$, $i \in \{t, s\}$ (normalization)
- 5: **end for**
- 6: $\tilde{\Delta} = \text{RANSAC}(\tilde{\Delta})$ (outlier rejection and averaging)
- 7: $\hat{f}_{\text{D,t}}$, \hat{v}^{tx} , $\hat{\eta} \leftarrow$ Algorithm 2 with input $\tilde{\Delta}$, α_t , $\{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_S\}$.

where $\Omega_s = \angle A_s - \angle A_{\text{LoS}}$, $\Omega_t = \angle A_t - \angle A_{\text{LoS}}$. The noise variables $w'_t[k]$ and $w'_s[k]$ reflect the impact of the CFO and PO removal and time-domain differencing operations. The phase offsets removal subtracts the phase of the LoS path from the phases of the other paths, hence increasing the variance of the noise on phase $i \in \{t, s\}$ to

$$\sigma_{\tilde{\phi},i}^2 = \sigma_{\phi,i}^2 + \sigma_{\phi,\text{LoS}}^2 = \frac{\sigma_h^2}{2} \left(\frac{1}{|A_i|^2} + \frac{1}{|A_{\text{LoS}}|^2} \right) = \frac{\sigma_h^2}{2} \kappa_i, \quad (12)$$

where we defined $\kappa_i = |A_i|^{-2} + |A_{\text{LoS}}|^{-2}$. Hence, $w'_i[k] \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\tilde{\phi},i}^2)$ with $i \in \{t, s\}$. This assumes that the noise on the phase of different paths is uncorrelated, which is true in SC systems using ideal autocorrelation sequences (such as the Golay sequences used in our experiments) or OFDM systems using full pilots in the frequency domain. As a result of the phase differencing operation with the LoS path, the noise variables on different paths become correlated, with covariance equal to $\sigma_{\tilde{\phi},\text{LoS}}^2 = \sigma_w^2 / (2G|A_{\text{LoS}}|^2)$.

Computing phase differences *cancel out* CFO and PO without estimating them, since they are common to all propagation paths. Despite the absence of CFO and PO in Eq. (10), the estimation of the target's Doppler frequency remains non-trivial due to the presence of the undesired frequency term $v^{\text{tx}}(\cos \xi_t - \cos \eta) / \lambda$ caused by the transmitter movement, as discussed in Section III-E.

B. Time-domain phase differencing

After CFO and PO cancellation, the RX computes first-order time-domain phase differences as

$$\Delta_i[k] = \angle \left(\frac{e^{j\tilde{\phi}_i[k]}}{e^{j\tilde{\phi}_i[k-1]}} \right) \quad (13)$$

with $i \in \{t, s\}$ and $k = 1, \dots, K - 1$. This step corresponds to line 3 of Algorithm 1. The phase differences are

$$\Delta_t[k] = 2\pi T_k \left(f_{\text{D,t}} + \frac{v^{\text{tx}}}{\lambda} (\cos \xi_t - \cos \eta) \right) + w'_t[k], \quad (14)$$

$$\Delta_s[k] = 2\pi T_k \left(\frac{v^{\text{tx}}}{\lambda} (\cos \xi_s - \cos \eta) \right) + w'_s[k], \quad (15)$$

where we recall that $T_k = t_k - t_{k-1}$. The time-domain phase differences cancel out the path-dependent constant phase terms Ω_s and Ω_t , which would otherwise prevent a comparison of the phases of the multiple paths. The time-domain differencing operation in Section IV-B doubles the noise variance with respect to Eq. (12), assuming the noise is uncorrelated and has constant variance across time steps k . Hence, the variance of the noise in Eq. (15) and Eq. (14) is $\sigma_{\tilde{\Delta},i}^2 = 2\sigma_{\phi,i}^2$ and $w'_i[k] \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\tilde{\Delta},i}^2)$, while the covariances among different paths are equal to $2\sigma_{\phi,\text{LoS}}^2$. Note that the temporal differencing also introduces correlation between the noise variables on *adjacent* values of the differences, i.e., $w'_i[k]$, $w'_i[k-1]$ and $w'_i[k+1]$, $w'_i[k]$. The covariance among adjacent differences is $\sigma_{2\Delta,i} = -\sigma_{\phi,i}^2$, while the one for non-adjacent ones is $\sigma_{k\Delta,i} = 0$ with $k = 3, \dots, K - 1$.

In Eq. (14) and Eq. (15), we assume that the inter-frame spacing for channel estimation, T_k , is sufficiently small so that the phase change between two subsequent frames is smaller than π , to avoid ambiguity. From Eq. (14), it can be seen that the noise-free phase differences Δ_i are upper bounded by $2\pi T_k(3f_{\text{max}})$, with $i \in \{t, s\}$ and f_{max} being the maximum Doppler shift caused by the TX (or the target). f_{max} is a system design parameter that can be set depending on the specific scenario and application. To fulfill the assumption, it is sufficient to impose $|\Delta_i| < \pi$ which yields $T_k < 1/(6f_{\text{max}})$. The choice of T_k is further discussed in Section V. Furthermore, to account for occasional fades or blockages that would cause noisy phase shifts, we implement the outlier detection strategy described in Section IV-E.

C. AoD-based simplification

By inspecting Fig. 2, a key simplification can be made in Eq. (14) and Eq. (15) noticing that $\cos \xi_i = \cos(\eta - \alpha_i) = \cos(\alpha_i - \eta)$, with $i \in \{t, s\}$. This substitution removes the dependency on the unknown and path-dependent angle ξ_i . The new expressions of the phase differences are

$$\Delta_t[k] = 2\pi T_k \left(f_{\text{D,t}} + \frac{v^{\text{tx}}}{\lambda} (\cos(\eta - \alpha_t) - \cos \eta) \right) + w'_t[k], \quad (16)$$

$$\Delta_s[k] = 2\pi T_k \left(\frac{v^{\text{tx}}}{\lambda} (\cos(\eta - \alpha_s) - \cos \eta) \right) + w'_s[k], \quad (17)$$

where the new dependency on $\alpha_i - \eta$, for $i \in \{t, s\}$, is easier to handle since the RX estimates α_i and the unknown term η is independent of the propagation paths. For convenience, we

further reformulate Eq. (16) and Eq. (17) as

$$\tilde{\Delta}_t[k] = f_{D,t} + \frac{v^{\text{tx}}}{\lambda} (\cos(\eta - \alpha_t) - \cos \eta) + \tilde{w}_t[k], \quad (18)$$

$$\tilde{\Delta}_s[k] = \frac{v^{\text{tx}}}{\lambda} (\cos(\eta - \alpha_s) - \cos \eta) + \tilde{w}_s[k], \quad (19)$$

where $\tilde{\Delta}_i[k] = \Delta_i[k]/(2\pi T_k)$, for $i \in \{t, s\}$ (line 4 in Algorithm 1). Dividing the phase measurements by the inter-frame spacing makes the noise variance depend on the specific frame k . Hence, the variances of the noise variables $\tilde{w}_t[k]$ and $\tilde{w}_s[k]$, termed $\sigma_{i,k}^2$, and their covariances, termed $\sigma_{i\ell,k}$, for $i, \ell \in \{t, s\}$ are respectively

$$\sigma_{i,k}^2 = \frac{\sigma_w^2 \kappa_i}{4\pi^2 GT_k^2}, \quad \sigma_{i\ell,k} = \frac{\sigma_w^2}{4\pi^2 GT_k^2 |A_{\text{LOS}}|^2}. \quad (20)$$

As discussed in Section III-D, Eq. (20) is based on the assumption that the SNR on the CIR is high. To validate the use of Eq. (20) in the derivation of the CRB, in Section V-C we performed simulations to assess that Eq. (20) models the actual noise variance on the input measurements to AsyMov.

Note that, since the RX estimates α_s and α_t , the number of unknowns is reduced from $S + 4$, i.e., $f_{D,t}, v^{\text{tx}}, \eta, \xi_t, \xi_1, \dots, \xi_S$, to 3, i.e., $f_{D,t}, v^{\text{tx}}, \eta$. This makes Eq. (14) and Eq. (15), for $s = 1, \dots, S$, a set of $S+1$ equations with 3 unknowns, which can be solved if the number of static multipath components satisfies $S \geq 2$, so that $S+1 \geq 3$. In the next section, we discuss the identifiability of our measurement model, then we detail our solver algorithm in Section IV-E.

D. Identifiability of the measurement model

To prove the identifiability of our model, we define the following vector quantities: the phase differences vector at the k -th frame, $\tilde{\Delta}[k] = [\tilde{\Delta}_t[k], \tilde{\Delta}_1[k], \dots, \tilde{\Delta}_S[k]]^T$, vector $\boldsymbol{\nu} = [f_{D,t}, v^{\text{tx}}]^T$, and the $(S + 1) \times 2$ matrix

$$\boldsymbol{\Gamma} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \lambda^{-1} (\cos(\eta - \alpha_t) - \cos \eta) \\ 0 & \lambda^{-1} (\cos(\eta - \alpha_1) - \cos \eta) \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & \lambda^{-1} (\cos(\eta - \alpha_S) - \cos \eta) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (21)$$

The measurement model can then be written as

$$\tilde{\Delta}[k] = \boldsymbol{\Gamma} \boldsymbol{\nu} + \mathbf{w}[k], \quad (22)$$

where $\mathbf{w}[k]$ is a complex-valued Gaussian noise vector with covariance matrix \mathbf{C}_k whose elements on the *diagonal* are the variances $\sigma_{i,k}^2$, while the off-diagonal elements are equal to $\sigma_{i\ell,k}$, as derived in Eq. (20).

Eq. (22) is a system of $S + 1$ equations in 3 unknowns. To prove the identifiability of $f_{D,t}, v^{\text{tx}}, \eta$, we verify whether in the absence of noise, Eq. (22) provides a unique set of measurements for each value assumed by the parameters. If η and v^{tx} are uniquely retrieved from equations 2, \dots , $S + 1$, i.e., only those pertaining to the static multipath components, then $f_{D,t}$ can be uniquely obtained from the first equation. Therefore, we analyze the identifiability of η and v^{tx} from equations 2, \dots , $S + 1$. These equations are of the form of Eq. (19) and each of them differs due to the angles α_s . The

coefficient v^{tx}/λ is common to all equations, so v^{tx} can be uniquely identified if η can. To ensure η is obtained without ambiguity, we must have *at least* 2 equations among the S equations involving static multipath components in Eq. (19) that do not degenerate into giving no information on η . This happens if there exists *at least* a pair of angles $\alpha_{s_1}, \alpha_{s_2}$, with indices s_1, s_2 , for which

- Condition 1: $\alpha_{s_1} \neq \alpha_{s_2}$
- Condition 2: $\alpha_{s_1} \neq 2\eta, \alpha_{s_2} \neq 2\eta$.

Note that violating either of the above two conditions means that one equation becomes uninformative on η . Since both η and α_s lie in the interval $[-\pi, \pi]$ by construction, we do not account for multiples of 2π in the above conditions. Our measurement model is hence identifiable except for a set of zero measure given by the values that violate the above conditions. Note that it is sufficient to have 2 angles α_s that satisfy the conditions. The latter *do not need to be* verified for all s to guarantee identifiability. Therefore, the more static multipath components are available, the lower the probability of encountering a pathological case for which the model is non-identifiable. In the solution algorithm detailed in the next section, we check that matrix $\boldsymbol{\Gamma}$ does not incur one of such cases during the iterations, hence avoiding ambiguity.

E. Doppler frequency estimation

To increase the robustness of AsyMov to outliers in the phase measurements, we pre-process them using the Random Sample Consensus (RANSAC) [38] algorithm. We use RANSAC to obtain a robust estimate of the mean phases within the processing window, $\bar{\Delta}_i, i \in \{t, s\}$, since phase differences of the same path are assumed constant during the time interval KT . The mean phases are collected in vector $\bar{\Delta} = [\bar{\Delta}_t, \bar{\Delta}_1, \dots, \bar{\Delta}_S]$ which contains the average values of $\bar{\Delta}_i[k]$ for $k = 1, \dots, K - 1, i = t, 1, \dots, S$, excluding the samples classified as outliers (line 6 in Algorithm 1). Then, we formulate the following non-convex optimization problem

$$\arg \min_{f_{D,t}, \eta, v^{\text{tx}}} \|\bar{\Delta} - \boldsymbol{\Gamma} \boldsymbol{\nu}\|_2^2 \quad (23)$$

$$\text{subject to } v^{\text{tx}} \geq 0, \eta \in [0, 2\pi]. \quad (24)$$

In Eq. (23), the variables $f_{D,t}, v^{\text{tx}}$ only appear in vector $\boldsymbol{\nu}$. Conversely, η only appears in $\boldsymbol{\Gamma}$. Our solution algorithm leverages such decoupled structure to alternatively optimize over the pair of variables $f_{D,t}, v^{\text{tx}}$ and then over η . We provide a thorough description of the algorithm next.

1) *Alternating minimization solution*: Assume that an initial estimate of η is available, denoted by $\hat{\eta}$. Considering the latter a fixed constant, the problem in Eq. (23) becomes a standard Least-Squares (LS) problem with a non-negativity constraint on v^{tx} . Denote by $\boldsymbol{\Gamma}(\hat{\eta})$ the matrix $\boldsymbol{\Gamma}$ in Eq. (21) computed using $\eta = \hat{\eta}$. By checking the rows of $\boldsymbol{\Gamma}(\hat{\eta})$, one can determine whether the current estimate, $\hat{\eta}$, violates the identifiability conditions discussed in the previous section. Specifically, if $\boldsymbol{\Gamma}(\hat{\eta})$ has 2 or more non-zero equal rows, this means Condition 1 is violated and only one of the equal rows should be retained. Instead, if $\boldsymbol{\Gamma}(\hat{\eta})$ contains any number of all-zero rows, Condition 2 is violated for such equations and such

rows should be removed from the matrix. In the following, we assume that this verification of the identifiability conditions is performed at each iteration of the algorithm when a new $\hat{\eta}$ is obtained. The problem is solvable with a unique solution as long as $S \geq 2$ static multipath components are available with angles that do not violate Conditions 1 and 2.

The LS problem is solved in closed form by computing

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\nu}} = \Pi(\mathbf{\Gamma}^\dagger(\hat{\eta})\bar{\mathbf{\Delta}}), \quad (25)$$

where the symbol \dagger denotes the pseudo-inverse of a matrix, $\hat{\boldsymbol{\nu}} = [\hat{f}_{D,t}, \hat{v}^{\text{tx}}]^\text{T}$ contains the estimates of the target Doppler frequency and TX movement speed, and $\Pi(\boldsymbol{\nu}) = [f_{D,t}, \max(0, v^{\text{tx}})]^\text{T}$ projects the LS solution onto the feasible set with $v^{\text{tx}} \geq 0$. The complexity of solving Eq. (25) is $\mathcal{O}(S^2)$ since the dimension of $\boldsymbol{\nu}$ is fixed to 2.

Conversely, when variables $f_{D,t}, v^{\text{tx}}$ are fixed, the problem reduces to finding the η that minimizes Eq. (23). Optimization over η can be efficiently carried out by a grid search in the bounded interval $[0, 2\pi)$. We construct grid $\mathcal{G} = \{0, 2\pi/N_\eta, \dots, 2\pi(N_\eta - 1)/N_\eta\}$ where N_η is the number of grid candidates and we solve

$$\hat{\eta} = \arg \min_{\eta \in \mathcal{G}} \|\bar{\mathbf{\Delta}} - \mathbf{\Gamma}\hat{\boldsymbol{\nu}}\|_2^2. \quad (26)$$

This approach has a complexity $\mathcal{O}(N_\eta S)$, which gives a total complexity of $\mathcal{O}(S^2 + N_\eta S)$. This is computationally affordable, since S is typically low in practice and η has bounded support, so the grid can be made fine-grained without excessively increasing its size. While alternative methods based on gradient descent could converge to local stationary points of the non-convex function, grid search guarantees that our solution is as close to the optimal value as determined by the grid step $2\pi/N_\eta$, which can be made arbitrarily small.

The above discussion motivates AsyMov's alternating minimization approach to solving the original problem in Eq. (23). The minimization proceeds as detailed in Algorithm 2, which is used in the last computational step of AsyMov, as shown in line 7 of Algorithm 1. In Algorithm 2, $(\cdot)^{(n)}$ denotes quantities at the n -th iteration and ϵ is a small positive constant.

The proposed approach converges to an approximation of a local minimum of the cost function following the result in [39], since: (i) the cost function is non-increasing across iterations, as proved in Appendix A, (ii) the optimization step to obtain $\hat{\boldsymbol{\nu}}$ is solved *optimally* with LS, (iii) the optimization step to obtain $\hat{\eta}$ approximates the optimal value with an error of at most $2\pi/N_\eta$ (the grid step), and (iv) the function $\mathbf{\Gamma}(\eta)$ is infinitely differentiable (smooth) and its derivative is bounded, being the sum of two sine functions. If N_η is sufficiently large, the algorithm is an instance of inexact (due to the grid search) block-coordinate descent with tight error bounds, and is guaranteed to converge to a local minimum of the cost function [39]. Notably, thanks to our initialization method based on a closed-form solution (Section IV-E2), which already provides a quite accurate estimate of the globally optimal parameters, local convergence is sufficient in practice to obtain accurate Doppler estimation and occurs in a few steps. The overall complexity of the minimization is $\mathcal{O}(N_{\text{it}}(S^2 + N_\eta S))$, where N_{it} is the number of iterations. Below, we provide a

Algorithm 2 Alternating minimization algorithm.

Input: Phase measurements $\bar{\mathbf{\Delta}}$, angles $\alpha_t, \{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_S\}$.

Output: Estimates of the parameters $\hat{f}_{D,t}, \hat{v}^{\text{tx}}, \hat{\eta}$.

- 1: Set $n = 0$, initialize $\hat{\eta}^{(0)}$ using Eq. (35) and $\hat{\eta}^{(-1)} = \infty$
 - 2: **while** $|\hat{\eta}^{(n)} - \hat{\eta}^{(n-1)}| > \epsilon$ **do**
 - 3: Fix $\hat{\eta}^{(n)}$ and obtain $\hat{f}_{D,t}^{(n+1)}, (\hat{v}^{\text{tx}})^{(n+1)}$ using Eq. (25)
 - 4: Fix $\hat{f}_{D,t}^{(n+1)}, (\hat{v}^{\text{tx}})^{(n+1)}$ and obtain $\hat{\eta}^{(n+1)}$ using Eq. (26)
 - 5: $n \leftarrow n + 1$
 - 6: **end while**
-

method to initialize $\hat{\eta}$.

2) *Closed form initialization of η* : Consider Eq. (19) with 2 phase measurements from static paths, i.e., $s \in \{1, 2\}$. We denote by $\bar{\Delta}_t, \bar{\Delta}_1$, and $\bar{\Delta}_2$ the time-averaged phase differences for the sensing path, and static paths 1 and 2. Using also Eq. (18), a system with 3 equations in 3 unknowns is attained, which can be solved to find an initialization of $\hat{\eta}$. We provide the solution in Appendix B, giving the full expressions of $\hat{\eta}$ in Eq. (35). As discussed in Section IV-D, the solution requires the following conditions to be met: (i) $\alpha_i \neq 0, i \in \{1, 2, t\}$, (ii) $\alpha_i \neq \alpha_\ell, i \neq \ell \in \{1, 2, t\}$, and (iii) $\alpha_i \neq 2\hat{\eta}, i \in \{1, 2\}$.

Note that violating conditions (i) and (ii) correspond to degenerate scenarios in which the LoS path is not available, or two static multipath components have the same AoD. Condition (iii) instead is violated if the AoD of one of the multipath components is equal to $2\hat{\eta}$.

V. ANALYSIS AND NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

In this section, we derive the CRB on the estimation of the parameters $f_{D,t}, \eta, v^{\text{tx}}$, based on the measurement model in Eq. (18) and Eq. (19). Then, we describe our simulations and the obtained numerical results. The CRB derivation differs from that of existing works for bi-static asynchronous ISAC, e.g., [30], [31], that do not consider the motion of TX and RX, since it is based on our new model in Eq. (22), which accounts for the inter-dependencies among paths introduced by the phase differencing operations.

A. Performance limits analysis

To assess bounds on the performance of the proposed Doppler frequency estimation method, we utilize the CRB [40], which represents a lower bound on the error variance of the parameter estimates. To this end, we define the vector containing all parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta} = [f_{D,t}, \eta, v^{\text{tx}}]^\text{T}$. In the CRB derivation, we assume no prior knowledge of the parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is available, and we consider each path's AoD to be known exactly since the latter is an input to our algorithm and must be obtained by other means. Moreover, to simplify the derivation and make the expressions more compact, we restrict to the case $S = 2$, i.e., two static paths are available, and we consider only a single time frame k . Extending the bound to an arbitrary K requires taking into account the covariances among adjacent temporal phase differences $\sigma_{2\Delta,i}$, given in Section IV-B, and is omitted for conciseness.

The likelihood of the vector measurement model in Eq. (22) is a multivariate Gaussian

$$p(\tilde{\mathbf{\Delta}}[k]; \boldsymbol{\theta}) \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{\Gamma}\boldsymbol{\nu}, \mathbf{C}_k) \quad (27)$$

where the parameters θ are contained in $\Gamma\nu$. \mathbf{C}_k has been defined in Section IV-D, and contains the variances and covariances from Eq. (20). Element i, ℓ of the Fisher Information Matrix (FIM), \mathbf{J} , is computed as in chapter 3.9, Eq. 3.31 of [40]

$$[\mathbf{J}]_{i,\ell} = \left[\frac{\partial \Gamma\nu}{\partial \theta_i} \right]^\top \mathbf{C}_k^{-1} \left[\frac{\partial \Gamma\nu}{\partial \theta_\ell} \right]. \quad (28)$$

We omit the full expression of the FIM for conciseness, and directly obtain the CRB by inverting it and taking the first element on the diagonal, $[\mathbf{J}^{-1}]_{1,1}$. The CRB on the Doppler frequency of the target is

$$[\mathbf{J}^{-1}]_{1,1} = \frac{\sigma_w^2 \zeta_{t,1,2}}{128\pi^2 G T_k^2 \sin^2\left(\frac{\alpha_1}{2}\right) \sin^2\left(\frac{\alpha_1 - \alpha_2}{2}\right) \sin^2\left(\frac{\alpha_2}{2}\right)}, \quad (29)$$

where $\zeta_{t,1,2}$ exhibits a complex dependency on $\kappa_t, \kappa_1, \kappa_2$, and the AoDs, $\alpha_t, \alpha_1, \alpha_2$. Its full expression is given in Appendix D, in Eq. (37). We observe that $[\mathbf{J}^{-1}]_{1,1} \rightarrow +\infty$ when $\alpha_1, \alpha_2 \rightarrow 2n\pi, n \in \mathbb{N}_0$ and $\alpha_1 \rightarrow \alpha_2$. This makes two of the equations in Eq. (22) equal, making the system underdetermined. Note that Eq. (29) does not contain v^{tx} and η , making it independent of the TX velocity vector. This means that the magnitude or direction of the TX velocity does not influence the error bound on the Doppler frequency.

B. Simulation setup

To validate AsyMov we perform simulations for 5 GHz, 28 GHz, and 60 GHz carrier frequencies f_c , as representative of, e.g., IEEE 802.11ax, Frequency Range 2 (FR2) 5G-NR, and IEEE 802.11ay systems, respectively. The coordinates of the target and static objects are randomly generated in a $d \times d$ empty mobility area, and the real CIR is obtained using Eq. (4). We simulate the transmission of the waveform used to perform channel estimation. For $f_c = 60$ GHz, an IEEE 802.11ay TRN field made of complementary Golay sequences is transmitted, while for $f_c = 5$ GHz and $f_c = 28$ GHz, we employ a random sequence of OFDM symbols modulated with BPSK. At the receiver, we add CFO, PO, and channel noise according to different SNR values. The received signal is sampled with period $1/B$ and the CIR is estimated. After the peak detection operation, the phases of the CIR peaks and the noisy AoD estimates, for each available path, are used as input to our algorithm. All the parameters are summarized in Tab. 1. The maximum TX speed, v_{max} , differs for each carrier frequency to reflect the typical speed of the corresponding use case, i.e., IEEE 802.11ax, 5G-NR and IEEE 802.11ay. Finally, to consistently compare various simulation configurations, we set the inter-frame spacing T_k to a fixed value $T_k = T = 1/(6f_{\text{max}})$, which is the maximum time gap allowed in the measurements to avoid phase ambiguity, as discussed in Section IV-B. We remark that the selected T is compatible with existing hardware and typical packet transmission times in wireless networks. The residual CFO is modeled as $f_o(kT) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_o^2)$ which depends on time index k because the phase drift accumulates at each new transmission. σ_o^2 is chosen such that the frequency shift in 1 ms is between ± 0.1 parts-per-million (ppm) of the

TABLE 1: Simulation parameters used in the numerical results. $\mathcal{U}(a, b)$ is the uniform distribution in the interval $[a, b]$. Values in curly brackets refer to parameters used for 60, 28, and 5 GHz carriers.

Target Doppler frequency [Hz]	$f_{D,t}$	$\pm \mathcal{U}(f_{\min}, f_{\max})$
Transmitter velocity [m/s]	v^{tx}	$\mathcal{U}(v_{\min}, v_{\max})$
Min. TX/target Doppler freq. [Hz]	f_{\min}	100
Min. TX/target velocity [m/s]	v_{\min}	0.5
Max. TX/target Doppler freq. [kHz]	f_{\max}	{1, 0.93, 0.3}
Max. TX/target velocity [m/s]	v_{\max}	{5, 10, 20}
Mobility area side [m]	d	{20, 50, 100}
Channel estimation period [ms]	T	{0.166, 0.178, 0.5}
Bandwidth [GHz]	B	{1.76, 0.4, 0.16}
Subcarrier spacing [kHz]	–	{_, 120, 78.125}
CFO time difference stand. dev. [MHz]	σ_o	{0.22, 0.12, 0.02}

carrier frequency f_c [41]. For the PO we assume the most stochastic scenario modeled as $\psi_o(kT) \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 2\pi)$. Note that our method cancels out the CFO and PO *exactly*, hence it is not significantly affected by their magnitude. The error on the AoD estimates is modeled as an additive Gaussian random variable with distribution $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_\alpha^2)$.

C. Noise distribution model and CRB validation

In Fig. 6, we compare the empirical distribution of the input measurements to Algorithm 2 obtained from our simulations with the theoretical one under the assumption of high SNR on the CIR. The theoretical distribution is Gaussian with zero mean and variance $\sigma_{i,k}^2, i \in \{t, s\}$, which is given in Eq. (20). Note that the input measurements to Algorithm 2 are no longer phases due to the division by $2\pi T_k$, and their unit of measure is s^{-1} . The empirical distribution is obtained from 1000 simulations with an SNR of 5 dB on the RX signal, and the IEEE 802.11ay scenario, with 60 GHz carrier frequency. Since the channel estimation process in IEEE 802.11ay involves combining multiple repetitions of complementary Golay sequences [21], the SNR gain of the channel estimation process is not straightforward to obtain. Therefore, we empirically computed the value of G , estimating SNR_h by comparing the estimated and the ground truth, noiseless CIR. Fig. 6a shows that the empirical noise distribution matches well with the theoretical one, validating our theoretical analysis of the noise distribution and the subsequent CRB. In Fig. 6b, we show the AsyMov Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and the related square-root CRB, $\sqrt{[\mathbf{J}]_{1,1}^{-1}}$, when transmitting at $f_c = 28$ GHz with an aggregation window of $K = 2$ samples. The RMSE of AsyMov does not reach the CRB, meaning it is not efficient, but scales similarly when increasing the SNR, decreasing with the same slope.

D. State-of-the-art comparison

To validate AsyMov, we compare it with Doppler estimation algorithms used in asynchronous bistatic ISAC systems. As stated in Section II, to the best of our knowledge, no other ISAC method tackles Doppler estimation with asynchronous and *moving* devices. Therefore, we define a benchmark algorithm that applies the technique proposed in JUMP [10] to remove the phase offsets, followed by the MUSIC algorithm to

Fig. 5: Target Doppler frequency estimation error varying the number of available static scatterers, the duration of the processing window, the SNR, and the AoAs measurements error, with $f_c = 60$ GHz, $f_c = 28$ GHz, and $f_c = 5$ GHz.

Fig. 6: In (a), the empirical measurements noise distribution (histogram) compared to the theoretical one, i.e., a Gaussian with zero mean and variance $\sigma_{i,k}^2$ from Eq. (20) (purple dashed line), with $f_c = 60$ GHz, SNR = 20 dB, $\sigma_\alpha = 5^\circ$, $KT = 16$ ms, and $S = 2$. In (b), the Doppler estimation RMSE of AsyMov compared to the square-rootCRB with $f_c = 28$ GHz and $K = 2$.

estimate the target Doppler frequency [18]. We call this benchmark JUMP-MUSIC (JM). Since JM does not account for the TX movement, it is biased by its Doppler frequency shift as discussed in Section III-E. The computational complexity of JM is $\mathcal{O}(K^3)$ due to the eigenvalue decomposition of the covariance matrix of the channel measurements in MUSIC.

E. Doppler frequency estimation performance

Since the possible Doppler frequencies vary for each considered f_c , to provide a fair comparison within different setups, we evaluate the performance of AsyMov against JM in terms of normalized absolute estimation error, defined as $\varepsilon_{f_{D,t}} = |f_{D,t} - \hat{f}_{D,t}|/|f_{D,t}|$.

1) *Number of static scatterers*: The number of available static scatterers S is of prime importance for the proposed algorithm, as detailed in Section IV-E. A minimum of $S = 2$ static paths are needed for the algorithm to admit a solution, whereas $S > 2$ increases its robustness to noise and reduces the probability of encountering one of the pathological cases in which the AoD of the paths violate the identifiability conditions in Section IV-D.

This is confirmed by the results in Fig. 5a, it is shown that the median estimation error and its spread are reduced if more static scatterers are available. For every considered carrier frequency, the median error lies below 5% of the actual Doppler frequency, even with SNR = 0 dB. We recall that

each scatterer adds one equation to the problem in Eq. (23) without increasing the number of unknowns. This improves robustness at the cost of higher complexity. In Fig. 5a, black diamonds represent the average time (across all f_c) to solve the minimization problem on an Intel Xeon Gold 6252N CPU.

2) *Processing window duration*: In Fig. 5b, we evaluate the impact of averaging phase measurements over a longer aggregation window. We underline that, since T differs for each carrier frequency, for a fixed observation interval KT , every considered f_c entails a different number of collected phases and AoD estimates. Increasing the number of considered frames K , while keeping T constant, clearly improves robustness to noise. However, the window duration can not be made arbitrarily large but has to be tuned depending on the dynamicity of the environment to ensure that the channel parameters remain constant through the whole observation interval KT . With $KT = 32$ ms, our method provides a median error below 1% of the true Doppler frequency for every considered f_c . On the other hand, JM is less dependent on an increasing number of considered frames because the error is dominated by the bias described in Section V-D. In addition, Fig. 5b provides a comparison between the time needed to estimate the target Doppler frequency by AsyMov and JM, represented by black diamonds and circles, respectively. As described in Section IV-E1, AsyMov's computational complexity is independent of K , while for JM it is $\mathcal{O}(K^3)$. Even for the smallest K , AsyMov is over 100 times faster than JM.

3) *Measurements error*: In Fig. 5c, we show the Doppler frequency estimation error as a function of the SNR, and of the noise affecting AoD measurements (σ_α). Lower SNR values greatly increase the estimation error spread, despite its median remaining below 0.02. Fig. 5c also shows that $\hat{f}_{D,t}$ is slightly affected by the AoD error, which means that the SNR level has a much stronger impact. Even though JM improves with higher SNR levels, AsyMov still outperforms it due to its capability of separating the target and the device Doppler.

Although our work focuses on Doppler frequency estimation, AsyMov also estimates η and v^{tx} . In Fig. 7, we show the normalized estimation errors for η and v^{tx} , which are respectively evaluated as $\varepsilon_\eta = |\eta - \hat{\eta}|/|\eta|$ and $\varepsilon_{v^{\text{tx}}} = |v^{\text{tx}} - \hat{v}^{\text{tx}}|/|v^{\text{tx}}|$, where $\hat{\eta}$ and \hat{v}^{tx} represent the estimated TX motion direction angle and the estimated TX speed.

4) *CIR measurement interval analysis*: As discussed in Section IV-B, T has to be sufficiently small to prevent am-

(a) Normalized η estimation error. (b) Normalized $v^{t,x}$ estimation error.
 Fig. 7: Varying SNR values, with $\sigma_\alpha = 5^\circ$, $KT = 16$ ms, and $S = 2$.

(a) Simulation with $f_c = 60$ GHz. (b) Experimental setup 1.
 Fig. 8: Average normalized Doppler frequency error.

biguity in the phase measurements. However, decreasing T makes the phase differences more sensitive to noise due to the structure of Eq. (20). So, a suitable tradeoff has to be identified. The impact of an increasing T on the estimation error due to the occurrence of phase ambiguities is evaluated in Fig. 8a. Here, T starts from the maximum value for which phase ambiguities are prevented. As expected, increasing T beyond this value causes a growth in the estimation error $\varepsilon_{f_{D,t}}$. Fig. 8a is obtained for $f_c = 60$ GHz by way of example, but similar results hold for other carrier frequencies.

VI. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this section, we present experimental results obtained by AsyMov on an IEEE 802.11ay-based ISAC testbed.

A. ISAC testbed

Our testbed consists of two ISAC nodes acting as TX and RX. Each node comprises a Xilinx RFSoc for baseband signal processing and a mmWave Siivers 16- or 8-elements phased array antennas operating at $f_c = 60$ GHz or $f_c = 28$ GHz, respectively. The implementation is based on that presented in [10]. We refer to [10], [42] for additional details on the testbed setup. The TX sends IEEE 802.11ay standard-compliant packets with 1.76 GHz bandwidth, including an IEEE 802.11ay header and a TRN field. This field contains 12 TRN units, each composed of 6 complementary Golay sequences [43]. We use each TRN unit to estimate the channel for a different TX beam pattern, scanning the whole angular space in front of the TX. This allows us to estimate the AoD of each multipath component with respect to the antenna array orientation, using the algorithm in [21]. The antenna beamwidth determines the resolution of the AoD estimation, which approximately equals 8° . The RX performs downconversion, sampling, packet detection, and symbol-level synchronization. To perform CIR estimation, we compute the cross-correlation of the received signal with the known TRN

units at the RX. Then, we apply peak detection to isolate significant multipath components and estimate AoD for each peak using the algorithm in [21]. We compensate for the TX orientation by estimating the AoD of the LoS path and removing it from the AoD of other paths.

This sensor has an acceleration measurement noise of ± 29.4 mm/s² over 1 ms, and a bias of 49 mm/s². We experimentally characterized the acceleration noise distribution through an Allan deviation plot, verifying that it is dominated by white noise. The IMU is used to obtain measurements of the TX velocity vector according to a reference frame centered on the TX device. Results obtained by integrating IMU measurements with our algorithm are presented in Section VI-D.

B. Experimental setup

The experiments are performed in a 5×4 m laboratory equipped with an infrared camera-based motion tracking system, as shown in Fig. 9. The camera system allows obtaining the accurate positions of each object in the environment to be used as a ground-truth reference. For this, we place infrared markers on the TX, RX, static reflectors, and targets. To evaluate AsyMov with mobile ISAC nodes, we mount the TX on a wheeled cart, moving it during the measurements. Fig. 10a and Fig. 10b describe the TX motion by plotting its position coordinates and its velocity components, respectively.

We consider 3 different evaluation setups, as described next. In all of them, the default carrier frequency is $f_c = 60$ GHz. In Setup 3 additional results using $f_c = 28$ GHz are presented.

- *Setup 1 (SU1)*. As shown in Fig. 9a, the first setup includes quasi-monostatic TX and RX, placed at a distance of 40 cm from one another and oriented towards the targets. In this setup, static and dynamic reflections are produced using metal whiteboards placed in the environment. The moving target whiteboard is mounted on a wheeled chair.

- *Setup 2 (SU2)*. A more challenging evaluation is conducted in a bi-static setting, with widely separated TX and RX, as shown in Fig. 9b. This experiment reproduces more realistic conditions where the LoS path is weaker and the orientation of the ISAC devices is unknown.

- *Setup 3 (SU3)*. Similarly to SU1, this setup includes quasi-monostatic TX and RX, 50 cm apart from one another and oriented towards the targets. However, as shown in Fig. 9c, this is a more realistic setup where the target is human and the static paths are produced by common office furniture, including a desktop computer and a desk. In addition, 1 or 2 people are moving in the same room besides the target, acting as *interferers*, to increase the similarity to a real office environment. The target subject carries a plastic plate on which we place the infrared markers. In this setup, we collect measurements with both $f_c = 60$ GHz and $f_c = 28$ GHz.

In all the considered experiments, the motion of the target and that of the TX follow *uncoordinated* back and forth trajectories (the TX movement trajectory is shown in Fig. 10). We do not use rails or stepped motors to simulate a realistic case where ISAC devices may be handheld and targets follow irregular trajectories. Unless specified, we consider the inter-frame duration T_k to be constant and denote it

(a) Setup 1 (quasi-mono-static), $S = 2$.

(b) Setup 2 (bi-static).

(c) Setup 3 (human target + moving interferers).

Fig. 9: Visualization of the experimental setup.

(a) TX position.

(b) TX velocity.

Fig. 10: Example TX position (a) and velocity (b) during movement. Blue and yellow colors refer to the x and y components, respectively.

by $T = 0.254$ ms. In Section VI-C1, we show that this simplification is not restrictive, since AsyMov is robust to a random choice of T_k . Furthermore, in the experiments, we re-analyze the choice of the inter-frame duration T to avoid phase ambiguities. As shown in Fig. 8b, due to the lower velocities involved, AsyMov achieves good performance on the experiments in Setup 1 for up to $T = 0.8$ ms. The performance degradation is minimal up to $T = 2.5$ ms due to the lower variations in Doppler frequencies observed in the experiments (as compared to the simulations), which leads to a lower probability of experiencing phase ambiguities. Finally, we recall that the simulation framework is not able to model all the nuisance sources occurring in a real system, like multipath fading, hardware non-idealities besides PO and CFO, and AoD estimation affected by non-Gaussian errors. All these aspects are instead present in our experiments and represent a more challenging validation scenario for AsyMov, which explains the gap between simulation and experimental results.

C. Doppler frequency and TX speed estimation error

AsyMov is evaluated in terms of absolute estimation errors on the target Doppler frequency, the TX speed, and η , respectively defined as $\hat{\epsilon}_{f_{D,t}} = |f_{D,t} - \hat{f}_{D,t}|$, $\hat{\epsilon}_{v^{tx}} = |v^{tx} - \hat{v}^{tx}|$, $\hat{\epsilon}_\eta = |\eta - \hat{\eta}|$. The ground truth $f_{D,t}$ is obtained by plugging into Eq. (3) the ground truth locations of the TX, the RX, and the target, obtained from the motion tracking system.

1) *Robustness to irregular inter-frame spacing*: In Fig. 11, we show the ground truth and the estimated target Doppler frequency for a specific experiment in Setup 1. We also show the results obtained with a random inter-frame spacing T_k . This case is implemented by randomly discarding CIR estimates in the experiment – each element is independently discarded with probability 0.5. AsyMov can accurately estimate the target Doppler frequency, with a marginal degradation despite

Fig. 11: Estimated target Doppler frequency, $\hat{f}_{D,t}$, with $S = 2$ and $KT = 16$ ms, for Setup 1.

a random T_k . Specifically, AsyMov obtains Doppler frequency estimation errors of 3.03 ± 3.61 Hz and 5.07 ± 6.66 Hz with constant and random T_k , respectively (mean \pm one standard deviation). The slight degradation of the latter (random) case is due to the fewer samples available in the observation window, as a consequence of the removal of CIR samples.

2) *State of the art comparison*: In Fig. 12, we compare AsyMov and JM error results, $\hat{\epsilon}_{f_{D,t}}$, in different setups using a mobile or static TX. We use $S = 2$ and $KT = 8$ ms or $KT = 48$ ms. For both SU1 and SU2 (Fig. 12a and Fig. 12b), the error obtained by AsyMov is only slightly higher with a moving TX compared to a static one. Conversely, JM achieves similar performance only in the case of a static TX. When the TX moves, the bias described in Section III-E hinders a correct target Doppler estimation, leading to a 195% and 45% higher median error with respect to AsyMov in SU1 and SU2, respectively. Furthermore, in Fig. 13 we show that AsyMov is also effective in a realistic environment with a human target, office furniture, and other moving people acting as interferers. As expected, the very low SNR on the target path due to the weak human body scattering at both 60 GHz and 28 GHz increases the error $\hat{\epsilon}_{f_D}$ with respect to Setups 1 and 2. However, AsyMov outperforms JM also in this case, especially when the TX is moving. JM achieves a median error which is approximately 290% higher than AsyMov's one at 60 GHz (Fig. 13a) and 56% higher at 28 GHz (Fig. 13b). In the latter case, the performance gap is smaller because the TX motion bias described in Section III-E is inversely proportional to the wavelength, so JM is less affected by the TX motion at lower frequencies when considering the absolute Doppler estimation error in Hz. This demonstrates that only AsyMov successfully copes with the motion of ISAC devices.

3) *TX velocity estimation*: Besides the target Doppler, AsyMov can additionally estimate the TX velocity. In Fig. 14, we

Fig. 12: Target Doppler frequency estimation error for different setups, with $S = 2$ and varying aggregation window KT .

Fig. 13: Target Doppler frequency estimation error and average computational time for different setups, with $S = 2$.

present both the velocity modulus and its direction. Fig. 14b shows that, with a sufficiently long window, i.e., 16 ms or longer, AsyMov achieves median errors lower than 5 cm/s for v^{tx} in all the presented setups. The error on the estimate of η in Fig. 14a, gets lower than 15° for Setups 1 and 2 with $KT \geq 16$ ms. For Setup 1 and 3, $\hat{\varepsilon}_\eta$ is affected by the difficulty of estimating the AoD for the LoS path, since the RX is located at the very edge of the field of view of the TX antenna. Additionally, the performance in Setup 3 is further affected by lower accuracy of estimating the AoDs for the weak paths scattered by a human body.

4) *Real-time implementation:* As we show in Fig. 5b, AsyMov execution time is from two to three orders of magnitude lower than JM. To assess the applicability of AsyMov in embedded devices, we tested it on a Nvidia Jetson TX2 board, measuring the time needed to estimate the Doppler frequency from the experimental measurements collected in Setup 3. The algorithm is implemented in Python, so its efficiency could be further optimized by implementing it in a lower-level programming language. In Fig. 13, we show, as black diamonds, the average time needed to estimate the target Doppler frequency in one aggregation window for different values of the window KT . The execution time with $KT = 48$ ms is below 100 ms in the worst case, proving that AsyMov obtains over 10 Doppler frequency estimates per second on embedded hardware.

D. Integration with IMU

Finally, we test the integration of our model with the TX velocity measured by the onboard IMU sensor. This is done by obtaining an estimate of v^{tx} from the IMU, in the reference system of the TX. Then, this velocity is used as an additional input to AsyMov, thus the number of unknowns is reduced to two and the system in Eq. (22) can be solved using a single static reference path. We remark that, having also a reliable estimate of η , the number of unknowns would be

Fig. 14: Varying the duration of the aggregation window, with $S = 2$.

Fig. 15: Target Doppler frequency with $S = 2$ and $KT = 16$ ms.

TABLE 2: Average target Doppler frequency estimation error \pm one standard deviation, with one undetected path within $[1.5, 2.1]$ s.

Error [Hz]	Time interval		
	$[0, 1.5]$ s	$[1.5, 2.1]$ s	$[2.1, 7.3]$ s
w/ IMU	5.32 ± 4.04	10.72 ± 12.32	6.51 ± 3.89
w/o IMU	2.06 ± 2.24	168 ± 518	2.91 ± 2.33

reduced to one, solving the system in Eq. (22) without any static reference path. However, the η estimate obtained from the IMU implemented in our experimental setup is rather unreliable, and its use is likely to degrade the estimation performance; thus, we do not integrate it in our results.

As shown in Fig. 15, integrating the TX speed measurement from the IMU could enhance the reliability of AsyMov. In this experiment, the CIR peak corresponding to one of the required static paths is not detected for several subsequent frames in the interval $[1.5, 2.1]$ s. Within this time interval, AsyMov lacks sufficient information (static paths) to estimate the target Doppler frequency and fails, as shown by the yellow curve. Conversely, when feeding the IMU measurement to AsyMov, the Doppler frequency is estimated accurately even when not all the CIR peaks are detected (pink curve). Interestingly, when all the required CIR peaks are available, AsyMov is more accurate *without* using the IMU measurement. This is evident from the zoom plot in Fig. 15 and from Tab. 2, where we quantitatively evaluate the Doppler estimation error for three different time intervals in the experiment of Fig. 15. While in the interval $[1.5, 2.1]$ s using the IMU gives a large performance gain, outside of this interval, estimating the Doppler solely based on the wireless channel cuts the estimation error by half with respect to using the IMU. Based on these results, the IMU should only be used to compensate for the temporary lack of a sufficient number of static multipath components.

VII. CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this paper, we proposed AsyMov, a method to estimate the Doppler frequency of a target in an *asynchronous* ISAC system featuring *mobile* ISAC devices. Our approach effectively disentangles the target's Doppler frequency from the phase offsets due to clock asynchrony and the Doppler caused by the device movement if at least 2 static multipath components are available. By exploiting phase differences across multipath components, across time, and the multipath geometry, AsyMov casts Doppler estimation as a non-linear least-squares problem that is solved through alternating minimization, attaining high-quality estimates for the target's Doppler frequency and the velocity of the moving ISAC device. In contrast with traditional MUSIC-based processing, AsyMov handles channel estimates obtained at irregular time intervals. Moreover, it can be seamlessly integrated with measurements from an IMU sensor, positioned on the moving ISAC device, to provide increased robustness as some of the static paths become temporarily unavailable. AsyMov has been thoroughly assessed via theoretical analysis, numerical simulation, and experiments on moving objects and human targets, showing comparable performance to static ISAC devices.

APPENDIX A

The proof that across the iterations Algorithm 2 the cost function in Eq. (23) is non-increasing proceeds by induction.

- *Base case* ($n = 0$): Denote by $\hat{\eta}^{(0)}$, $\hat{f}_{D,t}^{(0)}$, $(\hat{v}^{\text{tx}})^{(0)}$ as the closed form solution of Eq. (22), used as initial values for the unknowns. Using the notation $\Gamma^{(n)} = \Gamma(\eta^{(n)})$, we have

$$\left\| \bar{\Delta} - \Gamma^{(0)} \nu^{(0)} \right\|_2^2 \stackrel{(a)}{\geq} \left\| \bar{\Delta} - \Gamma^{(0)} \nu^{(1)} \right\|_2^2 \stackrel{(b)}{\geq} \left\| \bar{\Delta} - \Gamma^{(1)} \nu^{(1)} \right\|_2^2,$$

where (a) is because $\hat{f}_{D,t}^{(1)}$, $(\hat{v}^{\text{tx}})^{(1)}$ are the optimal solutions of the LS problem in Eq. (25) with fixed $\hat{\eta}^{(0)}$, while (b) follows from the definition of grid search in Eq. (26). The above chain of inequalities proves that in the first iteration, the cost function in Eq. (23) does not decrease.

- *Induction step*: Assume that the cost function does not decrease in the n -th step, i.e., $\left\| \bar{\Delta} - \Gamma^{(n)} \nu^{(n)} \right\|_2^2 \geq \left\| \bar{\Delta} - \Gamma^{(n+1)} \nu^{(n+1)} \right\|_2^2$. Then, since $\hat{f}_{D,t}^{(n+2)}$, $(\hat{v}^{\text{tx}})^{(n+2)}$ are the optimal solutions of Eq. (25) using $\eta^{(n+1)}$ and $\eta^{(n+2)}$ is obtained from the grid search in Eq. (26), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \left\| \bar{\Delta} - \Gamma^{(n+1)} \nu^{(n+1)} \right\|_2^2 &\geq \left\| \bar{\Delta} - \Gamma^{(n+1)} \nu^{(n+2)} \right\|_2^2 \geq \\ &\geq \left\| \bar{\Delta} - \Gamma^{(n+2)} \nu^{(n+2)} \right\|_2^2 \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

- *Conclusion*: Since both the base case and the induction step have been proved by mathematical induction, every iteration of Algorithm 2 does not increase the cost function.

APPENDIX B

We first observe that Eq. (19) does not contain the Doppler frequency of the target. Hence, we use it with $s = 1$ to obtain

write v^{tx} as a function of η (note that a similar expression is obtained using $s = 2$)

$$v^{\text{tx}} = \frac{\lambda \bar{\Delta}_1}{\cos(\eta - \alpha_1) - \cos \eta}. \quad (31)$$

Then, using the above result into Eq. (19) with $s = 2$, and solving for η we get

$$\tan \eta = \frac{\bar{\Delta}_2(\cos \alpha_1 - 1) - \bar{\Delta}_1(\cos \alpha_2 - 1)}{\bar{\Delta}_1 \sin \alpha_2 - \bar{\Delta}_2 \sin \alpha_1} \triangleq \xi. \quad (32)$$

Inverting the above equation as $\hat{\eta} = \arctan \xi$ would cause an ambiguity, since the codomain of the arctan function is $[-\pi/2, \pi/2]$. This would exclude from the solution the (valid) cases where $\eta \in [\pi/2, 3\pi/2]$. To resolve the ambiguity, we start by noticing that

$$\bar{\Delta}_1 \sin \alpha_2 - \bar{\Delta}_2 \sin \alpha_1 = \frac{v^{\text{tx}}}{\lambda} u(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) \cos \eta, \quad (33)$$

where $u(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) = \sin \alpha_1(1 - \cos \alpha_2) + \sin \alpha_2(\cos \alpha_1 - 1)$. Eq. (33) is obtained after some manipulations by substituting the expressions of $\bar{\Delta}_1$ and $\bar{\Delta}_2$. The left-hand side of Eq. (33) and $u(\alpha_1, \alpha_2)$ can be computed numerically using the phase measurements and the AoD estimates. Hence, we have that

$$\text{sign}(\cos \eta) = \text{sign} \left(\frac{\bar{\Delta}_1 \sin \alpha_2 - \bar{\Delta}_2 \sin \alpha_1}{u(\alpha_1, \alpha_2)} \right), \quad (34)$$

since v^{tx}/λ is positive by definition. From the sign of $\cos \eta$ we can understand whether $\eta \in [-\pi/2, \pi/2]$ (if $\cos \eta$ is positive) or $\eta \in [\pi/2, 3\pi/2]$ (if $\cos \eta$ is negative). This is then used to disambiguate Eq. (32) as follows, finding an initialization of η

$$\hat{\eta} = \begin{cases} \arctan \xi & \text{if } \cos \eta \geq 0, \\ \pi + \arctan \xi & \text{if } \cos \eta < 0. \end{cases} \quad (35)$$

APPENDIX C

The noise variance on the phase of path i is [44]

$$\sigma_{\phi,i}^2 = \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L} h_i[k, l_i]}{\partial \Re\{h_i\}} \right)^2 \frac{\sigma_h^2}{2} + \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L} h_i[k, l_i]}{\partial \Im\{h_i\}} \right)^2 \frac{\sigma_h^2}{2} \quad (36)$$

which gives $\sigma_{\phi,i}^2 = \sigma_w^2 / (2G|A_i|^2)$, meaning that the noise variance on the phase of a path is inversely proportional to the squared magnitude of that path.

APPENDIX D

Term $\zeta_{t,1,2}$ in the CRB expression in Eq. (29) is given by

$$\zeta_{t,1,2} = -\rho_{t,1,2} + \sum_{i \in \{t,1,2\}} \kappa_i [3 + \gamma(\{t,1,2\} \setminus i)], \quad (37)$$

where “ \setminus ” denotes the set subtraction operation, the expression of γ , function of a set of two indices $\{i, \ell\}$ is

$$\gamma(\{i, \ell\}) = 2 [\sin \alpha_i - \sin(\alpha_i - \alpha_\ell) - \sin \alpha_\ell]^2, \quad (38)$$

and $\rho_{t,1,2}$ is given in Eq. (39).

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$$\rho_{t,1,2} = \frac{16}{|A_{\text{LoS}}|^2} \left[\sin\left(\frac{\alpha_1}{2}\right) \sin\left(\frac{\alpha_2}{2}\right) \sin(\alpha_t) \left(\sin\left(\frac{\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - 3\alpha_t}{2}\right) - \sin\left(\frac{\alpha_1 - \alpha_2 - \alpha_t}{2}\right) - \sin\left(\frac{3\alpha_1 - \alpha_2 - \alpha_t}{2}\right) \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + \sin\left(\frac{\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - \alpha_t}{2}\right) + 2 \cos\left(\frac{\alpha_2}{2}\right) \sin\left(\frac{\alpha_1 - 2\alpha_2 + \alpha_t}{2}\right) \right) \right] \quad (39)$$

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